

Study: Perspective-Based Specification of Machine Learning-Enabled Systems.

Artifact: Transcription Focus Group

Date: 22/03/2022

This document presents an overview of the six software professionals who participated in the focus group and the transcriptions involved in our study. We include the explanation of our approach and the discussion with the participants.

Participants

Table I shows an overview of the participant characterization. It is possible to observe that all participants had more than 2 years of experience working with ML and participated in at least 2 of such projects.

Table I

Id	Role	# years	# ML projects
P1	Data Scientist	6	8
P2	Data Scientist	2	2
P3	Data Scientist	2	3
P4	Developer	2	4
P5	Developer	3	2
P6	Project Lead	2	2

We used the column 'Id' of Table I to identify the participants and their opinions. The moderator of the focus group was the first author of the paper and it is identified as 'Moderator' in this document. We highlighted the codes with green color resulting from our understanding about participants' positions.

We translated the focus group from Portuguese to English since the participants are Brazilian software practitioners. In the following, we present the transcriptions of the focus group.

Discussion with participants

Moderator: Guys, if you didn't understand some of the elements of our work, please let me know how I can help you. I can go back and explain again.

Now we want to hear from you about requirements in the context of ML-enabled systems. Based on your experience and the introduction presented today, how do you see the practical problems of this type of system from the requirements perspective?

P6: I've been working for just over 2 years with ML systems. I'm not an expert, but to the best of my knowledge, **there is a lack of tools and methods** (01 - lack of methods for supporting requirements for ML) that help in understanding and detailing these types of requirements. My feeling is that perhaps proposals of this type do not reach the industry. This leads to mismatches between practitioners and literature.

P3: I agree with Jairo, in my opinion, **there is a lack of methods** (01 - lack of methods for supporting requirements for ML) following this line. I've never, for example, seen a standard defined as a best practice for specifying and documenting ML-enabled systems.

P2: From my side, I see **lean inceptions as the closest thing to focused requirements for ML** (02 - other techniques for supporting requirements for ML). I know this approach is not focused on ML-based systems, but in my opinion it has worked well. I also know that it has its limitations, but this could be improved.

P4: ML is a process of continuous experimentation. This is well known. Requirements could not be different in this context. I see that the process of designing an ML-enabled system is based on empirical knowledge, which makes it highly dependent on **trial-and-error experimentation** (03 - need for experimentation). At the beginning of the projects, initial requirements are defined, but at the end of the project these requirements are very different. As projects progress, these requirements change. I think this uncertainty could be reduced to avoid reworks.

Moderator: Guys, now let's talk a little about the artifacts that were presented. The first was the ML Perspective-based diagram of tasks and concerns, and the second was the specification template. Feel free to bring up any element that you found important or relevant, but also any component that you consider could be improved or that was not clear.

P4: **I found your proposal super interesting** (04 - Positive position about our approach). In my view, the way we start to read and model is well mapped there, those initial conversations there to try to understand what is working in the context of the problem, define the objectives.

P6: I also **found it interesting** (04 - Positive position about our approach). I think **this maps well the process** that we follow in the company (05 - meaningful relationships). Really the content is quite extensive, a lot of information, but also mapped the ML process, the flow is very interesting. By looking at the task-concern relationships, I was able to identify dependencies and influences as explained. I think that's clear.

P2: I consider these perspectives very important and the overview provided by the diagram. I keep thinking: normally at the beginning of our ML projects, the team focuses on well-known requirements such as understanding the problem to be solved, obtaining data, and some

performance metrics that the model must achieve. Just that. As the team faces tasks, concerns arise that are not considered at the beginning of projects. This can negatively impact project management. **So I think this overview of ML that provides the approach is cool** (04 - Positive position about our approach).

P5: The idea is that whoever is working on the problem domain has the perspective diagram available to fill in the specification template, correct?

Moderator: Yes, the purpose of the diagram is to allow the requirements engineer or professional responsible for fulfilling these functions to analyze the different tasks and concerns from each perspective so that they can be analyzed with the different stakeholders. With this analysis done, the ML specification template can be filled with the components that apply.

P5: I didn't understand the ML tasks that have 2 colors. What is the purpose of that?

Moderator: Note that there are specific concerns that can benefit from involving more than one stakeholder in the analysis. For example, the execution engine concern is a yellow-blue gradient since it involves knowledge in charge of the data scientist and may also involve expertise of the software engineer that provides the ML-enabled system infrastructure.

P5: **I consider this resource of the proposal very important** (04 - Positive position about our approach). On many occasions, collaborative work is essential to be successful and achieve the value of what is planned. In ML projects this is of high importance as multidisciplinary teams need to communicate well.

P1: From what I've seen, using the ML diagram **allowed me to have an overview of the requirements that can be analyzed** from the early stages of the project and the requirements that are defined as the project progresses (05 - Overview of the process). But I had a doubt. Moderator, did **you ever consider a roadmap to answer these questions, tasks and concerns?** (06 - Improvements for our approach) For example: it would be nice to have a step-by-step, activity enumeration, template filling flow of the approach.

A roadmap would be very important to give an idea to those involved in the project about the activities that later on will have to be attended by X or Y professionals. So I see this diagram as a planner that can help ML teams identify upcoming tasks. But for that, you need to have a roadmap that allows you to map what is done first, what dependencies there are, what are the possible paths.

P3: Another point I would like to highlight is the following. I've worked on several projects developing the dashboards combining predictions and preferences of customers and users of the systems. Typically, I see user experience requirements take a back seat. Okay, we make an effort to identify some requirements at the beginning of the projects, but that's not enough in my opinion. **The relevance of UX in the success of this type of system forces us to reconsider this.** (07 - awareness on important concerns, 08 user experience perspective).

P5: It's true, P3. I also understand the need to consider data, model, user and infrastructure, but in my opinion, **the functional behavior of ML models, which is reflected in the goals and objectives, is crucial** (07 - awareness on important concerns). I think that's really the starting point of everything. This is where the team must really understand what the customer wants to determine how ML can help them to achieve their goals (09 - ML objective perspective).

Moderator: Very good guys, this feedback is very important for us. Now, regarding improvements, elements of the artifacts that are not clear, feel free to mention and express your ideas.

P4: Well, an ML project involves many activities, both technical and non-technical. **I think this could be reflected in the artifacts and made clearer, as differentiating the types of tasks, concerns in this case, helps to better address the responsibilities of those involved** (06 - Improvements for our approach).

Regarding the completeness of tasks and concerns, I feel that maybe something is missing. I don't know exactly what's missing, I just keep thinking that ML is a discipline that involves many areas such as mathematics, statistics, engineering... **so it would be good for you to review and evaluate if something is missing** (06 - Improvements for our approach).

Moderator: Got it, I agree with your point of view. In fact, the scope of our work did not consider dividing or differentiating this issue from technical tasks. An improvement of the approach could consider this. Thanks.

Guys, now we are going to fill out a questionnaire where you can mention the main benefits and limitations of using our approach. With this we also want to validate what was said here. Any questions please let me know.

In total, we identified the following list of codes attached to the transcription.

- 01 - lack of methods for supporting requirements for ML
- 02 - other techniques for supporting requirements for ML
- 03 - need for experimentation
- 04 - Positive position about our approach
- 05 - Overview of the process
- 06 - Improvements for our approach
- 07 - awareness on important concerns
- 08 - user experience perspective
- 09 - ML objective perspective